

European Nucleotide Archive

Metagenomics Standards and MAG Data Submissions

Maira Ihsan

Bioinformatician, EMBL-EBI

Joana Paupério

Biodiversity Project Manager, EMBL-EBI

Contents

- ENA Background
- Why submit data to the ENA?
- Data Structure at the ENA
 - ENA Data Model
 - ENA Metadata Model
 - Metagenomic Assembly Data Structure
- Data submission at the ENA
 - Webin-CLI Data Submission
- Submitting Assemblies
 - Registering Derived Samples
 - Submitting Metagenomic Assemblies
- Summary
- Workshop - Metagenomic data submission with Webin-CLI

ENA Background: What is ENA?

Open platform for the management, sharing, integration and dissemination of sequence data

- **Globally comprehensive scientific record** and European node of **INSDC**
- **Broad scope** covering raw data, through layers of interpretation and context
- **Connectivity** with broader EMBL-EBI resources
- Sequence data **foundation**
- Rich submission, discovery and retrieval **software, tools and services**
- **Support** through Helpdesk and training
- **Management**, sharing, integration and dissemination of sequence data
- **Data coordination** including project-specific data hubs and portals

Archive

Platform

Submitting data to the ENA

Why is it important to share data?

- Findability
- Accessibility
- Reproducibility/ReCanadability
- Interoperability
- Community collaboration
- Data standards

Maximum value

Submitting data to the ENA

All data in the ENA is submitted by members of the research community

What motivates people to submit?

- Open data
- Reproducibility
- ReCanadability
- 3rd party access
- Archival
- **Publication**
- Downstream analyses

*The data lifecycle, from ELIXIR Europe
<https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/>*

Data resources at EMBL-EBI

ENA - an ELIXIR Core Data Resource

- The ENA is part of the wider ecosystem of biodata resources
- Recognised as an ELIXIR CDR and Global Core Biodata Resource by the Global Biodata Coalition
- Integration into a system of biodata resources increases value in genomics data

GLOBAL
CORE
BIODATA
RESOURCE

Data Structure at ENA

ENA Data Structure

- ENA stores huge amounts of data
 - ... from many users
 - ... with samples from many taxa
 - ... who use many different techniques
 - ... and sequence on many different platforms
- But we need to display data in a consistent manner
- A robust model is the first step in achieving this

ENA Data model

Sequence data is organised into tiers:

- **Reads:** raw sequence data
- **Assemblies:** reconstructions of actual replicons
- **Annotations:** interpretations of biological function

Annotation and **assembly** are frequently paired

ENA Metadata Model

- Data without any context has no value
- Metadata tells us how sequence data was produced
- Makes it possible to compare datasets:
*“I want to see metagenome data from insect gut ..
... collected from Japan ...
... sampled between 2021 and 2023 ...
... compared with the same from the United Kingdom”*

- Archives have spent a lot of time thinking about this!

ENA Metadata Model: Study

- Lakes are heterogeneous ecosystems inhabited by a rich microbiome whose genomic diversity is poorly defined.
- Introduce a genome-resolved perspective of freshwater bacterial diversity across 6.5 million km² of Canada, the most lake-rich landscape on Earth.
- Resource for mapping the distributions of freshwater bacteria, tracing evolutionary transitions, tracking microbial dispersal and gene transfer from sources of pollution in human-altered watersheds.

Thomas Barrat/Dreamstime.com
Ablestock/Jupiterimages

ENA Metadata Model: Study

STUDY

ENA Metadata Model: Study

EMBL-EBI Services Research Training About us EMBL-EBI

ENA Webin Submissions Portal Support Manage Account Logou

Register study (project)

Submission Details

Release date [This is when your study will be made public.] *

Short descriptive study title *

Study Name

Detailed study abstract *

Will you provide functional genome annotation ?

PubMed Citations Registration

Add PubMed Citations

Study Attributes

Add Study Attributes

ENA Metadata Model: Study

EMBL-EBI Services Research Training About us EMBL-EBI

ENA Webin Submissions Portal Support Manage Account Logou

Register study (project)

Release date [This is when your study will be made public.] *
31-03-2027

Submission Details

Release date [This is when your study will be made public.] * Short descriptive study title *

Study Name Detailed study abstract *

Will you provide functional genome annotation ?

PubMed Citations Registration

Add PubMed Citations +

Study Attributes

Add Study Attributes +

ENA Metadata Model: Samples

Researchers collected 306 samples from lakes across Canada within 3 years between late June to mid-September.

Lake microbiome were sampled up to 2 m below the surface, and the details of each sample were logged in the database.

ENA Metadata Model: Sample

STUDY

Sample

Depth: 2m
Location: Canada
Sample 1

Sample

Depth: 0m
Location: Canada
Sample 2

Sample

Depth: 1m
Location: Canada
Sample 3

Sample

Depth: 2m
Location: Canada
Sample 12

Sample

Depth: 1.5m
Location: Canada
Sample 21

Sample

Depth: 1m
Location: Canada
Sample 10

Metadata Model: Sample Checklists

Minimum amount of information expected to describe biological samples required for registration in ENA

Sample Checklists

There is a minimum amount of information required during ENA sample registration and all samples must conform to a defined checklist of expected metadata values. The most suitable checklist for sample registration depends on the type of the sample.

These sample checklists have been developed to meet the needs of different research communities. Different communities have different requirements on the minimum metadata expected to describe biological samples. For any questions regarding checklists, contact us [here](#).

Filter by accession/name/description/field name

Accession	Name	Description
ERC000019	GSC MixS microbial mat biofilm	Genomic Standards Consortium package extension for reporting of measurements and observations obtained from the environment where the sample was obtained. By choosing the environmental package, a selection of fields can be made from a relevant subsets of the GSC terms.
ERC000020	GSC MixS plant associated	Genomic Standards Consortium package extension for reporting of measurements and observations obtained from the environment where the sample was obtained. By choosing the environmental package, a selection of fields can be made from a relevant subsets of the GSC terms.
ERC000021	GSC MixS sediment	Genomic Standards Consortium package extension for reporting of measurements and observations obtained from the environment where the sample was obtained. By choosing the environmental package, a selection of fields can be made from a relevant subsets of the GSC terms.
ERC000022	GSC MixS soil	Genomic Standards Consortium package extension for reporting of measurements and observations obtained from the environment where the sample was obtained. By choosing the environmental package, a selection of fields can be made from a relevant subsets of the GSC terms.
ERC000023	GSC MixS wastewater sludge	Genomic Standards Consortium package extension for reporting of measurements and observations obtained from the environment where the sample was obtained. By choosing the environmental package, a selection of fields can be made from a relevant subsets of the GSC terms.
ERC000024	GSC MixS water	Genomic Standards Consortium package extension for reporting of measurements and observations obtained from the environment where the sample was obtained. By choosing the environmental package, a selection of fields can be made from a relevant subsets of the GSC terms.
ERC000025	GSC MixS miscellaneous natural or artificial	Genomic Standards Consortium package extension for reporting of measurements and observations obtained from the environment where the sample was obtained. By choosing the environmental package, a selection of fields can be made from a relevant subsets of the GSC terms.

Metadata Model: Sample Checklists

- ENA metadata checklists guided by standards working groups and the communities
 - Keep up with requirements within communities
- Rich standardised metadata facilitates linking to source information
- General minimum requirements (INSDC)
 - Organism information mandatory and linked with NCBI taxonomy
 - INSDC spatiotemporal policy: mandatory provision of collection date & geographic location
 - INSDC missing value reporting

INSDC spatiotemporal metadata – minimum standards update (03-03-2023)

[Home](#) > [News & Announcements](#) > [INSDC spatiotemporal metadata – minimum standards update \(03-03-2023\)](#)

INSDC continues its aim to increase the number of sequences for which the origin of the sample can be precisely located in time and space through harmonisation of accurate geographical annotation and date and time of collection information.

ENA Sample Checklist Groups

Please select a checklist group first.

Environmental Checklists This group currently includes Genomic Standards Consortium (GSC) MixS sample checklists

Marine Checklists This group currently includes Micro B3 and Tara Oceans sample checklists

Other Checklists This group currently includes the ENA default sample checklist and a few project specific checklists

Pathogens Checklists This group currently includes several prokaryote and virus pathogen sample checklists

[Back](#)

[Next](#)

ENA Metadata Model: Sample – MlxS water

You have selected **GSC MlxS water**. Please select the checklist fields below.

Add custom field

Search fields

Mandatory Fields

Selection	Field Name	Validation	Units	Description
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	tax_id	Text field	None	Taxonomy ID of the organism as in the NCBI Taxonomy database . Entries in the NCBI Taxonomy database have integer taxon IDs. See our tips for sample taxonomy here
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	scientific_name	Text field	None	Scientific name of the organism as in the NCBI Taxonomy database . Scientific names typically follow the binomial nomenclature. For example, the scientific name for humans is <i>Homo sapiens</i> .
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sample_alias	Text field	None	Unique name of the sample. If not selected system will auto generate an unique alias
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sample_title	Text field	None	Title of the sample
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sample_description	Text field	None	Description of the sample
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	project name	Text field	None	Name of the project within which the sequencing was organized
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	collection date	Regular expression	None	The date the sample was collected with the intention of sequencing, either as an instance (single point in time) or interval. In case no exact time is available, the date/time can be right truncated i.e. all of these are valid ISO8601 compliant times: 2008-01-23T19:23:10+00:00; 2008-01-23T19:23:10; 2008-01-23; 2008-01; 2008.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	geographic location (latitude)	Regular expression	DD	The geographical origin of the sample as defined by latitude. The values should be reported in decimal degrees and in WGS84 system
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	geographic location (longitude)	Regular expression	DD	The geographical origin of the sample as defined by longitude. The values should be reported in decimal degrees and in WGS84 system

ENA Metadata Model: Sample – MixS water

You have selected **GSC MixS water**. Please select the checklist fields below.

Add custom field

Search fields

Mandatory Fields

Optional Fields

Selection	Field Name	Validation	Units	Description
<input type="checkbox"/>	trophic level	Permitted values	None	Trophic levels are the feeding position in a food chain. Microbes can be a range of producers (e.g. chemolithotroph)
<input type="checkbox"/>	observed biotic relationship	Permitted values	None	Description of relationship(s) between the subject organism and other organism(s) it is associated with. E.g., parasite on species X; mutualist with species Y. The target organism is the subject of the relationship, and the other organism(s) is the object.
<input type="checkbox"/>	known pathogenicity	Text field	None	To what is the entity pathogenic, for instance plant, fungi, bacteria
<input type="checkbox"/>	relationship to oxygen	Permitted values	None	Is this organism an aerobe, anaerobe? Please note that aerobic and anaerobic are valid descriptors for microbial environments
<input type="checkbox"/>	propagation	Text field	None	The type of reproduction from the parent stock. Values for this field is specific to different taxa. For phage or virus: lytic/lysogenic/temperate/obligately lytic. For plasmids: incompatibility group. For eukaryotes: sexual/asexual. Mandatory for MIGs of eukaryotes, plasmids and viruses.
<input type="checkbox"/>	sample collection device	Text field	None	The device used to collect an environmental sample. It is recommended to use terms listed under environmental sampling device (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/ENVO) and/or terms listed under specimen collection device (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/GENEPIO_0002094).
<input type="checkbox"/>	sample collection method	Text field	None	The method employed for collecting the sample. Can be provided in the form of a PMID, DOI, url or text.
<input type="checkbox"/>	sample storage temperature	Regular expression	°C	temperature at which sample was stored, e.g. -80
<input type="checkbox"/>	sample storage location	Text field	None	Location at which sample was stored, usually name of a specific freezer/room. Indicate the location -----

ENA Metadata Model: Experiments

DNA was extracted from filters.

Library preparation using the NEBNext Ultra II DNA Library prep kit.

Sequenced 150 bp paired-end shotgun sequencing on an Illumina NovaSeq 6000 platform.

ENA Metadata Model: Experiments

ENA Metadata Model: Runs

The result of these 6 paired end experiments is 12 FASTQ files.

These are compressed and uploaded to a database, where they undergo processing and wait to be made public.

```
@SRR2960126.1 1/1
GCCAGCTATATCAGTTTCCTTTGTGATGGGGCGTTTATGTAAGGGATGGGTATGGAACGCACCCCTGGCTAGAACGAAAAGACTTGCTAT
TGTGAAGTTA
+
=;?AD=D?FDB???ACGHGGEHCEEHC@GDG>GDGHFF@9?C<38BFEACHIID>EEC>A3@D;?=:ABCA?
@@A8=B=B>89>ACCCACCADC3@4@@A
@SRR2960126.2 2/1
GTGGGTAACATTTGGAACAGAAAAACAAAAGTAGAATGGTGGGTGAGGAGAACAATAAAAAATGATACTTCATTTAATTATCATTTAGA
GATGTATATC
+
CCCFDFDFHHHHHIJIIJJJJJJJJJJII?
DGIJJJJBFIFFGGIJJIIJJJJHHHHHHFFFFFDEEEEDFEDEEEDEEEEDDDDDDEEFFDD
@SRR2960126.3 3/1
CTTTTAAACAAAGATTTTTTAAAAAATGCTGTGCTGTAATCTACTAGCAAAAACTAATTTGCTAGTTGCATTGGAAGATATTGATACT
TGACAATTTA
+
CCFFFFFHDFGHHHJIIJJIIJJJJIIJIGHIIJJJJIIJJJJJJJJIGJIHGHHHHHFFFFFEDCCADCDEEEDDD
DDDDDDDDDD
@SRR2960126.4 4/1
GCTTTTTTTCGGCAACGATGGAATCGATCAATTGTTATTGTGACAGCTAAATTGATAAAACAAAATGATACAGTTTCAAACCTGATCAAAA
ATTTGCAGCA
+
@=?DDDBDFBHD<FBHAHBD@FGIEDHGH?7BB9BFGHIDF@====FCGEGGGH3AEHC;@@DDF@C>;A@AC:
5-5;>@C@CCC::@ACBA@C:4>:(2
```

ENA Metadata Model: Runs

ENA Metadata Model: Runs

You have selected **Fastq File Type**. Please select the checklist fields below.

Show Description

Search fields

Mandatory Fields

Selection	Field Name	Field Label	Permitted Value	Description
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sample	Sample		Sample alias or accession.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	study	Study		Study alias or accession.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	instrument_model	Instrument model	Permitted values ▾	The sequencing instrument model used in the experiment
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	library_name	Library name		The name for the library if any.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	library_source	Library source	Permitted values ▾	The type of source material that is being sequenced.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	library_selection	Library selection	Permitted values ▾	The method used to select for or against, enrich, or screen the material being sequenced.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	library_strategy	Library strategy	Permitted values ▾	The sequencing technique intended for this library.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	library_layout	Library layout	Permitted values ▾	The library layout specifies whether to expect single or paired configuration of reads.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	forward_file_name	Forward file name		Please enter compressed fastq the file name including any subdirectory name
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	forward_file_md5	Forward File checksum		The file MD5 checksum. This field is mandatory if you do not use the Webin File Uploader or upload the checksum using a .md5 file.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	reverse_file_name	Reverse file name		Please enter compressed fastq the file name including any subdirectory name
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	reverse_file_md5	Reverse file checksum		The file MD5 checksum. This field is mandatory if you do not use the Webin File Uploader or upload the checksum using a .md5 file.

ENA Metadata Model: Results

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/home>

Project: **PRJEB29238**

The NSERC Canadian LakePulse Network is a scientific initiative assessing environmental issues affecting Canadian lakes. Through multidisciplinary projects, LakePulse researchers use tools in lake science, spatial modelling, analytical chemistry, public health, and remote sensing to assess the status of over 600 lakes across various ecozones in Canada. The impacts of land-use, climate change and contaminants on lake health will be assessed to develop policies for better lake management.

Secondary Study Accession: ERP111525
Study Title: Epipelagic bacterial communities of Canadian lakes
Center Name: Centre for Structural and Functional Genomics
Study Name: Bacterial communities of Canadian lakes
ENA-FIRST-PUBLIC: 2022-09-12
ENA-LAST-UPDATE: 2022-09-12

General

View: XML
XML (STUDY)
Download: XML
XML (STUDY)
Cross References: Show
Publications: Show
ORCID Data Claims: Show
Related ENA Records: Show

Navigate around the object

Read Files

Data

Read Files: Hide

Navigate on data

Show Column Selection

Download report: JSON TSV

Get download script

Download selected files

Download All

Study Accession	Sample Accession	Experiment Accession	Run Accession	Tax Id	Scientific Name	Generated FASTQ files: FTP	Sub
PRJEB29238	SAMEA7614180	ERX4739145	ERR4869703	256318	metagenome	<input type="checkbox"/> ERR4869703_1.fastq.gz	<input type="checkbox"/> 0
						<input type="checkbox"/> ERR4869703_2.fastq.gz	<input type="checkbox"/> 0
PRJEB29238	SAMEA7614191	ERX4739146	ERR4869704	256318	metagenome	<input type="checkbox"/> ERR4869704_1.fastq.gz	<input type="checkbox"/> 0
						<input type="checkbox"/> ERR4869704_2.fastq.gz	<input type="checkbox"/> 0

Information for a single run

Tags

xref
EuropePMC

Project description and metadata

Run-centric data table

ENA Metadata Model: Navigation Bar

- View project metadata
- Show/hide different information about project
- Explore cross-references related to project
- Explore reads/analyses files

General

View:	XML
	XML (STUDY)
Download:	XML
	XML (STUDY)
Cross References:	Show
Publications:	Show
ORCID Data Claims:	Show
Related ENA Records:	Show

Data

 Read Files: Hide

ENA Metadata Model: Results

Project: PRJEB29238

The NSERC Canadian LakePulse Network is a scientific initiative assessing environmental issues affecting Canadian lakes. Through multidisciplinary projects, LakePulse researchers use tools in lake science, spatial modelling, analytical chemistry, public health, and remote sensing to assess the status of over 600 lakes across various ecozones in Canada. The impacts of land-use, climate change and contaminants on lake health will be assessed to develop policies for better lake management.

Secondary Study Accession: ERP111525
Study Title: Epipelagic bacterial communities of Canadian lakes
Center Name: Centre for Structural and Functional Genomics
Study Name: Bacterial communities of Canadian lakes
ENA-FIRST-PUBLIC: 2022-09-12
ENA-LAST-UPDATE: 2022-09-12

Related ENA Records

Result	Count
Experiment	368
Run	368

General

View: XML
XML (STUDY)

Download: XML
XML (STUDY)

Cross References: Show

Publications: Show

ORCID Data Claims: Show

Related ENA Records: Hide

Data

Read Files: Show

Tags

▼ xref

> EuropePMC

ENA Metadata Model: Results

Experiment: ERX4739146

Illumina NovaSeq 6000 paired end sequencing

Organism: [metagenome](#)

Experiment Accession: ERX4739146

Instrument Platform: ILLUMINA

Instrument Model: Illumina NovaSeq 6000

Center Name: Centre for Structural and Functional Genomics

Library Layout: PAIRED

Library Strategy: WGS

Library Source: METAGENOMIC

Library Name: LakePulse

Library Selection: RANDOM

Show More

Read Files

Show Column Selection

Download report: [JSON](#) [TSV](#)

Get download script

Download selected files

Download All

Study Accession	Sample Accession	Experiment Accession	Run Accession	Tax Id	Scientific Name	Generated FASTQ files: FTP	Sub
PRJEB29238	SAMEA7614191	ERX4739146	ERR4869704	256318	metagenome	<input type="checkbox"/> ERR4869704_1.fastq.gz	<input type="checkbox"/> 0
						<input type="checkbox"/> ERR4869704_2.fastq.gz	<input type="checkbox"/> 0

General

View: [XML](#)

Download: [XML](#)

Cross References: [Show](#)

ORCID Data Claims: [Show](#)

Data

Read Files: [Hide](#)

Tags

environment by geolocation

terrestrial

New tags feature

Annotations of ENA objects

Controlled textual annotations provided to metadata objects to facilitate search and filtering

The Metadata Model: Sample - Taxonomy

Taxon: 256318
metagenome [species]

Lineage
unclassified sequences, metagenomes

Tax Tree

Abbreviated lineage

- > unclassified sequences
- > metagenomes
- > ecological metagenomes
 - activated carbon metagenome [species]
 - activated sludge metagenome [species]
 - aerosol metagenome [species]
 - air metagenome [species]
 - alkal sediment metagenome [species]
 - anaerobic digester metagenome [species]
 - archaeline metagenome [species]
 - ant fungus garden metagenome [species]
 - aquaculture metagenome [species]
 - aquatic metagenome [species]
 - aquifer metagenome [species]
 - ballast water metagenome [species]
 - beach sand metagenome [species]

Taxon: 256318
metagenome [species]

Lineage
unclassified sequences, metagenomes

Tax Tree

Abbreviated lineage

- > unclassified sequences
- > metagenomes
- > ecological metagenomes
 - metagenome [species]
- > organismal metagenomes
 - algae metagenome [species]
 - amphibian metagenome [species]
 - annelid metagenome [species]
 - ant metagenome [species]
 - aquatic viral metagenome [species]
 - bat metagenome [species]
 - beetle metagenome [species]
 - bird metagenome [species]
 - blood metagenome [species]
 - bovine gut metagenome [species]
 - bovine metagenome [species]

View: XML
Download: XML
Navigation: Show
Tax Tree: Hide
Related ENA Records: Show

View: XML
Download: XML
Navigation: Show
Tax Tree: Hide
Related ENA Records: Show

- The taxon ID is an essential attribute of your ENA samples
- Make sure you use environmental taxonomy

Lake metagenome

Taxonomy ID: 3413140

Scientific name: **lake metagenome**

Inherited blast name: **metagenomes**

Rank: **species**

metagenome

Taxonomy ID: 256318

Scientific name: **metagenome**

Inherited blast name: **metagenomes**

Rank: **species**

ENA Metadata Model: Analysis

The Metadata Model: Analysis - usually...

```
>ENA|PEHZ01000001|PEHZ01000001.1 Insect metagenome contig_0_374_CA-Am, whole genome shotgun sequence.
GATACGTTGTCAGGTGCAAGGGTATGTGCATGGAGGGTGCCTGTATAGGTGCGAGGATG
TGTGGGGTGTGTAGGTGGAAGTGTGTGTGCATGGAGGATACGTGTGCAGGTGCAAGGGTA
TGTGCATGGAGGGTGCCTGTATAGTCCGAGGATGTGTGGGGTGTGTAGGTGCGAGGGT
GTGTGTAGGGGGTGTGTAGGTGTGAGTGTGTATGTGCATGGAGGGTGTGCAGGTGCAA
GGGTATGTGCATGGAGGGTGCCTGTATAGTCCGAGGATGTGTGGGGTGTGTAGGTGTG
AGGGTGTGTGTAGGGGGTGTGTAGGTGTGAGTGTGTATGTGCATGGAGGGTGTGCAGG
TGCAAGGGTATGTG
>ENA|PEHZ01000002|PEHZ01000002.1 Insect metagenome contig_2_497_CA-Am, whole genome shotgun sequence.
GACCATCTAGCGACCTCCACATACTAGGGTTAAAATACCCTAAAGTAGAAGCAAAAGTTA
ATATATTAACGCATAACTATGAGATACTATTTCTCTGTTATGAAAATGATTAAGGATTAG
TATGAGAATCTACGGGTTTTCTATTTTCATCTGAGTTTATGCTGGAGTCTATTATATCTA
TTTTAACGAGAATAAAGAAACCTAGATACTTTTAAACACAAAGAGATATTAACAATTT
CTATTCACGTTTTATTTAGTAGGTATGAATTAAGATACTATCTAAGATTCAATTAATTCAT
AATGAAAGAAAATGAATGGTTAGAAAAAGAAAATAAAAACTTTCATTTACTTCTAGAATC
TGGTAGTAACCTAATAGAGATGATAATTTGATTTATCATGCCAAAGATTATAGCGGAGTT
AAAAATAGTGAAGTAAAAATTGACCAAGTTTCAGTGGAGGTCGCTAGATGGTCCGGGTTAGGTG
GAGTCCCTAGATGGTC
>ENA|PEHZ01000003|PEHZ01000003.1 Insect metagenome contig_4_469_CA-Am, whole genome shotgun sequence.
GACCATCTAGCGACCTCCACATCATTGCGCTAAATGCAGTTCTGGATGCTTTGTTGGACTT
TTCCATGAAGTGATGTTTCTCCATCATCGACAGTCAATGTTGTACGCGAATCAGGAATC
GTAGTGCATTGACTCACCGAGTCATCATCGGGCTGACTGTGCATGAACTAATCGTG
TCTGATGCATGAAAGGTACTGGGCCAATTTGTGCGACCGAATTTGAAAAGTACGCCGTACC
TCAGGAATCATCGGTGGGAACTTTGTAAAAACATCAGTGTCTATTTAACAAGACGT
TTGAAAAGGGCGCATCCGGCCACAGGGTCTTTAAGCTCAGTATTTGCCACAGTATCAGAA
AACCGGCAATACTAAACAGACCCGCTGCTGCGTTTGAATAATCCTTCCAACAAGGCCCTT
CTTCGTCATTTGATCGAAATGGGGCCTGGTGGAGGTCGCTAGATGGTC
>ENA|PEHZ01000004|PEHZ01000004.1 Insect metagenome contig_8_628_CA-Am, whole genome shotgun sequence.
GACCATCTAGCGACCTCCACTCAAACCTCCAAAGGTGATTTGCTAGCTTAAAAATACCCAC
TATCGCTATCGTAATGAATTTCTATCTTGAATCTCACTACCTGGTTTTTCAGCGGCTTTAA
```

In non-metagenomic cases..

Read data for one of the samples can be put through an assembly program to produce a set of contigs.

The Metadata Model: Analysis - usually...

Structuring Metagenomic Studies: Metadata Model

- The metadata model ensures submission to ENA always includes certain essential information
- There are some complications when we submit metagenomic assemblies ...

Structuring Metagenomic Studies: Types Of Metagenomic Assembly

Primary assembly

Binned assembly

Metagenome-Assembled Genome (MAG)

Structuring Metagenomic Studies: Types Of Metagenomic Assembly

Structuring Metagenomic Studies: Types Of Metagenomic Assembly

Primary assembly: contigs assembled from reads, with no attempt made to classify contigs taxonomically

Binned assembly: single-taxon set of sequence derived from a primary metagenome, from contig level up to a full genome assembly

Metagenome-Assembled Genome (MAG): a binned metagenome of high quality, low contamination, and classified to a unique organism

What is considered a MAG in ENA?

A Metagenome-Assembled Genome (MAG) is a single-taxon assembly based on one or more binned metagenomes that has been asserted to be a close representation to an actual individual genome (that could match an already existing isolate or represent a novel isolate).

MAG submissions are submitted at the same level as isolate genomes and are distributed within INSDC in the same way. As an environmental sample can contain many duplicate genomes of the same organism and as MAG assemblies are more prone to contamination, we request only the highest quality unique-taxon submissions are submitted as MAGs.

There should only be **one MAG submitted for each species** within a biome. This can be determined using a **de-replication** step or by choosing the **highest quality representative** genome for each predicted species.

Archiving

Metagenome Assembly Workflow

Archiving

Metadata: XML

Metadata: XML
Submitted fastq
Standard fastq

Metadata: XML
Submitted fasta
Standard fasta

Metadata: XML
Submitted fasta/flatfile
Standard fasta/flatfile

Metadata: XML
Submitted fasta/flatfile
Standard fasta/flatfile

Structuring Metagenomic Studies: Primary Assemblies

Structuring Metagenomic Studies: Binned Assemblies

Binned Assemblies: Sample Checklist

You have selected **ENA binned metagenome**. Please select the checklist fields below.

Add custom field

Search fields

Mandatory Fields

Selection	Field Name	Validation	Units	Description
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	tax_id	Text field	None	Taxonomy ID of the organism as in the NCBI Taxonomy database . Entries in the NCBI Taxonomy database have integer taxon IDs. See our tips for sample taxonomy here
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	scientific_name	Text field	None	Scientific name of the organism as in the NCBI Taxonomy database . Scientific names typically follow the binomial nomenclature. For example, the scientific name for humans is <i>Homo sapiens</i> .
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sample_alias	Text field	None	Unique name of the sample. If not selected system will auto generate an unique alias
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sample_title	Text field	None	Title of the sample
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sample_description	Text field	None	Description of the sample
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	metagenomic source		None	The metagenomic source of the sample. This value should contain "metagenome" and be in the taxonomy database e.g. wastewater metagenome or human gut metagenome. Please note "metagenome" alone will not be accepted. Check here for more details on metagenome taxonomy: https://ena-docs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/faq_taxonomy.html#environmental-taxonomic-classifications
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sample derived from	Regular expression	None	Reference to parental sample(s) or original run(s) that the assembly is derived from. The referenced samples or runs should already be registered in INSDC. This should be formatted as one of the following. A single sample/run e.g. ERSxxxxxx OR a comma separated list e.g. ERSxxxxxx,ERSxxxxxx OR a range e.g. ERSxxxxxx-ERSxxxxxx
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	project name	Text field	None	Name of the project within which the sequencing was organized
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	binning software	Text field	None	Tool(s) used for the extraction of genomes from metagenomic datasets, where possible include a product ID (PID) of the tool(s) used. E.g. MetaCluster-TA (RRID:SCR_004599) or MaxBin (biotools:maxbin)
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	binning parameters	Text field	None	The parameters that have been applied during the extraction of genomes from metagenomic datasets e.g. coverage and kmer
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	isolation_source	Text field	None	describes the physical, environmental and/or local geographical source of the biological sample from which the sample was derived
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	collection date	Regular expression	None	The date the sample was collected with the intention of sequencing, either as an instance (single point in time) or interval. In case no exact time is available, the date/time can be right truncated i.e. all of these are valid ISO8601 compliant times: 2008-01-23T19:23:10+00:00; 2008-01-23T19:23:10; 2008-01-23; 2008-01; 2008.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	geographic location (country and/or sea)	Permitted values	None	The geographical origin of where the sample was collected from, with the intention of sequencing, as defined by the country or sea name. Country or sea names should be chosen from the INSDC country list (http://insdc.org/country.html).
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	geographic location (latitude)	Regular expression	DD	The geographical origin of the sample as defined by latitude. The values should be reported in decimal degrees and in WGS84 system
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	geographic location (longitude)	Regular expression	DD	The geographical origin of the sample as defined by longitude. The values should be reported in decimal degrees and in WGS84 system

Structuring Metagenomic Studies: MAGs

MAGs: MIMAGs Sample Checklist

You have selected **GSC MIMAGs**. Please select the checklist fields below.

Add custom field

Search fields

Mandatory Fields

Selection	Field Name	Validation	Units	Description
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	tax_id	Text field	None	Taxonomy ID of the organism as in the NCBI Taxonomy database . Entries in the NCBI Taxonomy database have integer taxon IDs. See our tips for sample taxonomy here
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	scientific_name	Text field	None	Scientific name of the organism as in the NCBI Taxonomy database . Scientific names typically follow the binomial nomenclature. For example, the scientific name for humans is Homo sapiens.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sample_alias	Text field	None	Unique name of the sample. If not selected system will auto generate an unique alias
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sample_title	Text field	None	Title of the sample
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sample_description	Text field	None	Description of the sample
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	metagenomic source		None	The metagenomic source of the sample. This value should contain "metagenome" and be in the taxonomy database e.g. wastewater metagenome or human gut metagenome. Please note "metagenome" alone will not be accepted. Check here for more details on metagenome taxonomy: https://ena-docs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/faq_taxonomy.html#environmental-taxonomic-classifications
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sample derived from	Regular expression	None	Reference to parental sample(s) or original run(s) that the assembly is derived from. The referenced samples or runs should already be registered in INSDC. This should be formatted as one of the following. A single sample/run e.g. ERSxxxxxx OR a comma separated list e.g. ERSxxxxxx,ERSxxxxxx OR a range e.g. ERSxxxxxx-ERSxxxxxx
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	project name	Text field	None	Name of the project within which the sequencing was organized
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	completeness score	Regular expression	%	Completeness score is typically based on either the fraction of markers found as compared to a database or the percent of a genome found as compared to a closely related reference genome. Completeness score is one of 3 attributes which in combination reflect the standard quality of a MAG, see here for more information: https://ena-docs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/faq_metagenomes.html . Mandatory for all

Structuring Metagenomic Studies: MAGs

Structuring Metagenomic Studies: MGnify

- MGnify offers an automated pipeline for the analysis and archiving of microbiome data to help determine the taxonomic diversity and functional & metabolic potential of environmental samples.
- Users can submit their own data for analysis or freely browse all of the analysed public datasets held within the repository. In addition, users can request analysis of any appropriate dataset within the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA).

Structuring Metagenomic Studies: MAGs

MGNify submitted TPA MAG

Assembly: GCA_965149225.1

The Third Party Annotation (TPA) assembly was derived from the primary data set PRJNA861716

Comment

This is a Third Party Annotation (TPA) bin derived from the primary whole genome shotgun (WGS) data set SRP387787. This sample represents a Metagenome-Assembled Genome (MAG) from the metagenomic run SRR20550370.

Organism: uncultured *Prevotella* sp.
Assembly Name: SRR20550370_concoct_43
Assembly Title: SRR20550370_concoct_43 assembly for uncultured *Prevotella* sp.
Assembly Level: contig
Genome Representation: full
Accession: GCA_965149225
Total Length: 2467301
Ungapped Length: 2467301
N50: 93540
Spanned Gaps: 0

Show More

General

View: XML
Download: XML
All Seq EMBL
All Seq FASTA
WGS Set EMBL
WGS Set FASTA
Cross References: Show
ORCID Data Claims: Show
Assembly Statistics: Show
WGS Sequence Set: CBCTRD01

Tags

pathogen
bacterium

User submitted MAG

Assembly: GCA_905235535.1

Metagenomic data was generated for rumen contents samples taken from two domesticated ruminant species (cattle and sheep) and two non-domesticated species (reindeer and red deer). This data was used to generate metagenome assembled genomes and to enable the taxonomic and functional comparison of the microbiota of these species.

Organism: uncultured Bacteroidales bacterium
Assembly Name: RUG30236
Assembly Title: RUG30236 assembly for uncultured Bacteroidales bacterium
Assembly Level: scaffold
Genome Representation: full
Accession: GCA_905235535
Total Length: 1994095
Ungapped Length: 1994062
N50: 19618
Spanned Gaps: 1

Show More

General

View: XML
Download: XML
All Seq EMBL
All Seq FASTA
WGS Set EMBL
WGS Set FASTA
Cross References: Show
ORCID Data Claims: Show
Assembly Statistics: Show
WGS Sequence Set: CAJOLS01

Tags

environment by geolocation
terrestrial

Data Submission at ENA

Data Submission at ENA

- There are three submissions routes
- *'Interactive Submission'*:
 - Use your browser to fill out web forms describing your work
- *'Programmatic Submission'*:
 - Describe your work in XML documents, submit them to us using cURL
- *'Webin-CLI'*:
 - Smart submission interface, made in-house

Data Submission: Interactive

- Register your objects using your browser
- Familiar and largely accessible
- Prepare spreadsheets for bigger submissions

ENA Webin Submissions Portal

Support | Manage Account | Logout (Webin-60876)

Register study (project)

Submission Details

Release date [This is when your study will be made public.]*
22-05-2024

Short descriptive study title*
Testing de novo mutation calling artefacts by re-sequencing single mutation accumulation

Detailed study abstract*
To test for the possibility that mutation bias results could in part be artifacts of a pooled-seedling sequencing approach, we re-sequenced entire rosettes of siblings (individual plants) of one mutation accumulation line and asked if the distribution of variation called (i.e., putative somatic mutations around transcription start and termination sites) was similar to the patterns seen with the seedling pools of the 107 individual lines described in the preceding section. Specifically, we grew 10 siblings and extracted DNA from 3-week old whole rosettes. Barcoded PCR-free libraries for

Study Name
Arabidopsis mutation accumulation

Will you provide functional genome annotation?

PubMed Citations Registration

Add PubMed Citations +

PubMedid	Title	Remove
9784120	Arabidopsis thaliana: a model plant for genome analysis.	

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J
1	Checklist	ERC000013	GSC MIXS host associated							
2	tax_id	scientific_name	sample_alias	sample_title	sample_description	sample derived from	collection date	geographic location (country and/or sea)	geographic location (latitude)	geographic location (longitude) by
3	#units								DD	DD
4										
5										

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L
1	FileType	fastq	Read submission file type									
2	sample	study	instrument_model	library_name	library_source	library_selection	library_strategy	library_layout	forward_file_name	forward_file_md5	reverse_file_name	reverse_file_md5
3												
4												

Data Submission: Programmatic

- Prepare an XML/JSON file describing your submission
- Send this to us via HTTPS
- Correct format for JSON/XML files important for successful submission and validation of data.

- Example cURL command:

```
curl -u username:password \  
-F "SAMPLE=@sample.xml" \  
-F "SUBMISSION=@submission.xml" \  
"https://wwwdev.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/drop-box/submit/"
```

```
<SUBMISSION>  
  <ACTIONS>  
    <ACTION>  
      <ADD/>  
    </ACTION>  
  </ACTIONS>  
</SUBMISSION>
```

```
<SAMPLE_SET>  
<SAMPLE alias="MYS176V2" center_name="">  
  <TITLE>human gastric microbiota, mucosal</TITLE>  
  <SAMPLE_NAME>  
    <TAXON_ID>129436</TAXON_ID>  
    <SCIENTIFIC_NAME>stomach metagenome</SCIENTIFIC_NAME>  
    <COMMON_NAME></COMMON_NAME>  
  </SAMPLE_NAME>  
  <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTES>  
    <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
      <TAG>collection date</TAG>  
      <VALUE>2010</VALUE>  
    </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
    <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
      <TAG>host body site</TAG>  
      <VALUE>Mucosa of stomach</VALUE>  
    </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
    <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
      <TAG>human-associated environmental package</TAG>  
      <VALUE>human-associated</VALUE>  
    </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
    <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
      <TAG>geographic location (latitude)</TAG>  
      <VALUE>1.81</VALUE>  
      <UNITS>DD</UNITS>  
    </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
    <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
      <TAG>geographic location (longitude)</TAG>  
      <VALUE>-78.76</VALUE>  
      <UNITS>DD</UNITS>  
    </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
    <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
      <TAG>geographic location (country and/or sea)</TAG>  
      <VALUE>Colombia</VALUE>  
    </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
    <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
      <TAG>geographic location (region and locality)</TAG>  
      <VALUE>Tumaco</VALUE>  
    </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
    <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
      <TAG>environment (biome)</TAG>  
      <VALUE>soast</VALUE>  
    </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
    <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
      <TAG>project name</TAG>  
      <VALUE>test12V2</VALUE>  
    </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
    <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
      <TAG>environment (feature)</TAG>  
      <VALUE>human-associated habitat</VALUE>  
    </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
    <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
      <TAG>environmental medium</TAG>  
      <VALUE>gastric fluid</VALUE>  
    </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
    <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
      <TAG>broad-scale environmental context</TAG>  
      <VALUE>human gut</VALUE>  
    </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
    <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
      <TAG>local environmental context</TAG>  
      <VALUE>human gut</VALUE>  
    </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
    <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
      <TAG>ENA-CHECKLIST</TAG>  
      <VALUE>ERC000015</VALUE>  
    </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
  </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTES>  
</SAMPLE_SET>
```


ENA - Submission Tools & Data Portals

Metagenome Data Submission with Webin-CLI

Webin-CLI Data Submission: Webin Portal

Welcome to the Webin Submissions Portal

You can use this service for a range of submission activities as well as reports on your submissions. For help with submitting your data, including the use of this interface, please refer to our Help Guides. Please familiarise yourself with the different options available. New users are advised to take a moment to understand the interface.

•Studies tab

- Used for registering studies and viewing/editing metadata for pre-registered studies

•Samples tab

- Used to register new samples, requesting taxonomy for novel/unidentified/published species and viewing/editing metadata for pre-registered samples

•Raw reads/experiments tab

- Used to register runs/experiments and viewing/editing metadata for pre-registered runs/experiments
- Can also be used to track run files validation/processing

•ENA Metadata Model showing data objects and data structure

Studies (Projects)

Studies Report

- + Register Samples
- + Register Novel Taxonomy
- + Submit XMLs (advanced)

Samples

Samples Report

Raw Reads (Experiments and Runs)

- + Submit Reads
- + Submit XMLs (advanced)

- Runs Report
- Run Files Report
- Run Processing Report
- Unsubmitted Files Report

Data Analyses

Assemblies and annotated sequences must be submitted with Webin-CLI. Other analyses can be submitted as XMLs.

- + Generate Annotated Sequence Spreadsheet
- + Submit XMLs (advanced)
- Analyses Report
- Analysis File Report
- Analysis Processing Report

•Analyses tab

- Used to download annotated sequences template spreadsheet and view submitted analyses metadata.
- Can also be used to track analyses files processing.

Webin-CLI Data Submission: Webin Account

- Each submission requires a Webin account.
- Can be created by submitting web form on the Webin Portal page.
- Requires fields such as centre name, country and user credentials.
- Fields such as centre name, contact information can be updated.
- Metagenomics consent box to allow MGnify to access and analyse metagenomic data.

Account Details

Abbreviated center name	Password
Full center name	Confirm Password
Laboratory Name	
Address	
Country	

Contact Information

Add At Least One Contact

No Sensitive Data

I confirm that the data submitted through this account is NOT sensitive, restricted-access or human-identifiable.

Metagenomics Consent

By keeping this box checked you give consent to the EBI MGnify team to analyse those data for which you have requested a pre-publication confidential hold. Note that the data as well as the analysis results will remain confidential until the specified release date of the associated sequencing study. If you are also requesting assembly of your data by MGnify, you also give consent to MGnify to submit these assemblies to your ENA study on your behalf. MGnify will not change any metadata or data you have already submitted but may need to perform updates to submissions performed by their team in exceptional circumstances. This service provides pre-publication state-of-the-art analysis results, along with visualisations, that you may use in subsequent publications. The service is described in <http://europepmc.org/article/MED/31696235> and we kindly request, should you use these analyses in your publications, that you cite this paper.

I give consent and confirm that the data submitted through this account is NOT sensitive, restricted-access or human-identifiable

Save Cancel

Webin-CLI Data Submission: Study

- Study required for each submission at the ENA.
- Needs to be registered interactively or programmatically. Webin-CLI does not support study registration.
- Groups data objects under one project.
- Authority on release date of data objects linked to a study.
- Add publications and study attributes to study metadata.

Webin-CLI does not support study registration

The screenshot shows a web form titled "Submission Details". It contains several input fields: "Release date [This is when your study will be made public.] *", "Study Name", and "Short descriptive study title". There is a checkbox labeled "Will you provide functional genome annotation?". Below these fields is a "Detailed study abstract" text area. At the bottom of the form, there are sections for "PubMed Citations Registration" with a link "Add PubMed Citations" and "Study Attributes" with a link "Add Study Attributes". "Submit" and "Cancel" buttons are located at the bottom right of the form.

```
<PROJECT_SET>
  <PROJECT alias="cheddar_cheese">
    <NAME>WGS Streptomyces iranensis</NAME>
    <TITLE>Characterisation of Microbial Diversity and...</TITLE>
    <DESCRIPTION>This study aimed to characterise the interaction of microbial...</DESCRIPTION>
    <SUBMISSION_PROJECT>
      <SEQUENCING_PROJECT/>
    </SUBMISSION_PROJECT>
  </PROJECT>
</PROJECT_SET>
```

Webin-CLI Data Submission: Sample

- Samples can now be registered with Webin-CLI (in JSON file format)
- Interactive and programmatic sample submission more widely used with reads.
- Range of sample checklists to choose from including Environmental, Pathogen, Plant and Marine checklists.
- Include required, recommended and mandatory metadata fields.
- Mandatory minimum metadata fields for all checklists include taxonomy information, sample details, collection dates and geographic location.

```

"samples": [
  {
    "alias": "uniqueAlias",
    "title": "human gut microbiota, mucosal",
    "organism": {
      "taxonId": "408170"
    },
    "attributes": {
      {
        "tag": "project name",
        "value": "human gut study"
      },
      {
        "tag": "collection date",
        "value": "2010-01-20"
      },
      {
        "tag": "host body site",
        "value": "Mucosa of stomach"
      },
      {
        "tag": "human-associated environmental package",
        "value": "human-associated"
      },
      {
        "tag": "geographic location (latitude)",
        "value": "1.81",
        "unit": "DD"
      },
      {
        "tag": "geographic location (longitude)",
        "value": "-78.76",
        "unit": "DD"
      },
      {
        "tag": "geographic location (country and/or sea)",
        "value": "Colombia"
      },
      {
        "tag": "geographic location (region and locality)",
        "value": "Tumaco"
      },
      {
        "tag": "environment (biome)",
        "value": "Coast"
      },
      {
        "tag": "environment (feature)",
        "value": "human-associated habitat"
      },
      {
        "tag": "environmental medium",
        "value": "gastric fluid"
      },
      {
        "tag": "broad-scale environmental context",
        "value": "human gut"
      },
      {
        "tag": "local environmental context",
        "value": "human gut"
      },
      {
        "tag": "ena-checklist",
        "value": "ENC000013"
      }
    }
  }
]

```

```

{
  "study": "PRJEB12345",
  "sample": {
    {
      "alias": "sediment_sample",
      "title": "Sample derived from sediment in Antarctica",
      "organism": {
        "taxonId": "77133"
      }
    },
    "attributes": [
      {
        "tag": "collection date",
        "value": "2025-01-30"
      },
      {
        "tag": "geographic location (country and/or sea)",
        "value": "Antarctica"
      },
      . . .
    ]
  },
  "name": "ena-EXPERIMENT-TEST-28-10-2024-01-02:26:880-109",
  "platform": "ILLUMINA",
  "instrument": "Illumina MiSeq",
  "insert_size": "390",
  "libraryName": "unspecified",
  "library-source": "GENOMIC",
  "library_selection": "PCR",
  "libraryStrategy": "AMPLICON",
  "fastq": {
    "value": "test_single_run_2.fastq.gz",
    "attributes": {
      "read_type": ["single"]
    }
  }
}

```

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J
1	Checklist	ERC000013	GSC MixS host associated							
2	tax_id	scientific_name	sample_alias	sample_title	sample_description	sample derived from	collection date	geographic location (country and/or sea)	geographic location (latitude)	geographic location (longitude) br
3	#units							DD		DD
4										
5										

Webin-CLI Data Submission: Sample

Webin-CLI Data Submission: Run

- Raw read sequencing data object, final step for submission of raw reads.
- Submit reads using a manifest file in plain text or JSON format.
- Only BAM, CRAM and Fastq file formats for raw read data supported by Webin-CLI.
- Validates files before submission.
- Successful submission returns a run accession with the sequence files metadata and an experiment accession with the library metadata.

manifest.txt

```
STUDY ERP013289
SAMPLE ERS980556
NAME ena-EXPERIMENT-TEST-13-03-2025-01:02:26:880-109
INSTRUMENT Illumina MiSeq
INSERT_SIZE 390
LIBRARY_SOURCE GENOMIC
LIBRARY_SELECTION PCR
LIBRARY_STRATEGY AMPLICON
FASTQ test_single_run.fastq.gz
```

manifest.json

```
{
  "study": "ERP013289",
  "sample": "ERS980556",
  "name": "ena-EXPERIMENT-TEST-28-10-2024-01:02:26:880-109",
  "platform": "ILLUMINA",
  "instrument": "Illumina MiSeq",
  "insert_size": "390",
  "libraryName": "unspecified",
  "library-source": "GENOMIC",
  "library_selection": "PCR",
  "libraryStrategy": "AMPLICON",
  "fastq": {
    "value": "test_single_run.fastq.gz",
    "attributes": {
      "read_type": ["single"]
    }
  }
}
```

Webin-CLI Data Submission: Assembly

Primary metagenome assembly submitted as contig level in the form of FASTA file.

Binned and MAG assemblies require derived sample submission with assembly.

Assembly data can be submitted with Webin-CLI using TXT/JSON manifest files.

```
{
  "study": "PRJEB55033",
  "sample": "SAMEA116086104",
  "assemblyname": "ena-assembly-EMBL-EBI-test",
  "platform": "Illumina HiSeq 2000",
  "run_ref": "ERR11274686",
  "assembly_type": "Metagenome-Assembled Genome (MAG)",
  "program": "FlyHit v2.1.9",
  "coverage": "85.56",
  "moleculetype": "genomic DNA",
  "fasta": {
    "value": "MAG.fasta.gz"
  }
}
```

STUDY	PRJEB71679
SAMPLE	ERS31315282
RUN_REF	ERR14790848
ASSEMBLYNAME	MAG_test
ASSEMBLY_TYPE	Metagenome-Assembled Genome (MAG)
COVERAGE	90
PROGRAM	FlyHit v2.1.9
PLATFORM	Illumina HiSeq 2000
FLATFILE	MAG.embl.gz

Submitting Data: Webin-CLI

- Anatomy of a command:


```
holt@w10-L-ZLLMV2:~/workshop_2$ webin-cli -manifest test1_manifest.txt -context genome -username Webin-256 -password $password -validate
INFO : Your application version is 2.1.0
INFO : Webin-CLI version 2.0.0 adds a mandatory requirement for genome assembly submissions to include an ASSEMBLY_TYPE field
INFO : Creating report file: /home/holt/workshop_2/./webin-cli.report
INFO : The submission has been validated successfully.
```

Webin-CLI Data Submission

Submission steps

Interface

Assembly types:

- primary metagenome
- binned metagenome
- Metagenome-Assembled Genome (MAG)

Example three-tiered metagenome assembly project in ENA

Summary

<http://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/>

- The ENA provides **scientific record** of sequencing data.
- Established in the early 1980s, extended for **new technologies and applications**.
- Comprehensive record of world's **nucleotide sequencing information** covering raw read data, sequence assembly information and functional annotation.
- Presents large amounts of a diverse range of data in a consistent manner, making use of **data and metadata Models**.
- Metadata model requires minimal mandatory metadata in line with **FAIR data principles**.
- Rich submission, discovery and retrieval **software, tools and services**.
- **Support** through Helpdesk and training.
- **Data submission** routes: Interactive, programmatic and Webin-CLI.
- Webin-CLI Submission using **manifest files** submitted with the command line.
- **Data coordination** including project-specific data hubs and portals.

Handy links

- ENA Browser: <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/home>
- ENA Submission/Retrieval Guide: <https://ena-docs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/submit/general-guide.html>
- ENA Helpdesk: <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/support>
- Advanced Search: <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/advanced-search>
- Webin Portal: <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/webin/login>
- Webin TEST Portal: <https://wwwdev.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/webin/login>

Thank you

Any Questions?

Metagenomic Data Submission Practical

During this exercise, you will implement some of the skills you have just learnt and submit some metagenomic data to the ENA.

1. Register a Study interactively
2. Register your environmental sample interactively
3. Submit runs with webin-CLI
4. Submit primary metagenome assembly with webin-CLI
5. Submit binned assembly and sample with webin-CLI
6. Submit MAG and sample with webin-CLI

Thank you
Any Questions?

